

STUDIES ON CERAMIC RAW MATERIALS. PART II. REDUCTION OF FERRIC IRON BY FELDSPARS

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Ferric compounds, whether inherent or artificially impregnated, suffer reduction in feldspar melts. The mechanism of such reduction has been explained and supported by experimental evidences. The relative activities of sodium and potassium feldspars in this respect have been compared and the reduction has been found to take place to a greater extent in orthoclase than in albite. Probable explanations for this have been offered. The colour of the fused mass varies depending on the ratio of ferric to ferrous iron and on the nature of the iron compounds produced. Regarding the chemical nature of the fused mass, it has been suggested that the iron perhaps enters the structure and yields a solid solution of iron analogue of anorthite in iron orthoclase. This fused mass, however, has been found to be very suitable for brown glaze for stoneware or for porcelain bodies.

The influence of accompanying minerals on the iron colours of fired clays had been investigated by many workers. These studies were confined to lime (Seger, "Collected Writings", I, p. 115), alumina (Kinnison, *Trans. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, 1914, 16, 136; Orton, *ibid.*, 1903, 5, 389; Seger, *loc. cit.*, p. 109), carbon (Orton, *loc. cit.*, pp. 389, 390) and fluxes (Seger, *loc. cit.*, p. 107; Bancroft, "Applied Colloid Chemistry", 1926, p. 241). Of these the effect of fluxes deserves special attention. It is, however, a matter of common experience that a sample of clay may produce red, brown, buff, or nearly white colour on being fired, but there is invariably a deepening of the colour when vitrification progresses. This effect is more pronounced if the proportion of fluxes in clay is appreciable and the temperature is sufficiently high. Wilson ("Ceramics, Clay Technology", 1927, p. 161) holds the view that at low temperatures the amount of fused materials is small and the bright colours are produced by the suspension of the unfused Fe_2O_3 particles. Fusion progresses as the temperature is increased. The fused mass then exerts its solvent action on the oxides and produces thereby different shades of colours, depending on the extent of actual solution and on the amount of fluxes present. The explanation offered by Seger (*loc. cit.*) is also analogous. He attributes the light colours of easy-fired wares to the porous condition of the body and the consequent dilution of the red colour with air. Vitrification reduces the porosity and enclosed air and the red particles are brought closer together whereby the colour is deepened. The above explanation appears to be not above criticism.

Firstly, it is easy to conceive the deepening of colour due to accumulation of red particles at the vitrification temperatures, but it is rather inconceivable that the red colour of iron should change to yellow-brown, or dark and chocolate reds and finally into black, due primarily, to a physical phenomenon like dissolution. Secondly, these studies were confined to the combined influences of fluxes and, as such, it was very difficult to follow precisely the chemical changes, if any, during the vitrification stage.

The feldspars, grouped as flux, may occur in clays as impurities, but they are purposely used in whiteware bodies and glazes. Amongst the chief types of feldspars,

the potash variety is known to exhibit a longer and safer temperature range. This has therefore found wide application for body-work requiring a high degree of vitrification. For glaze work, the albite and even the plagioclase are widely used, as they give good results. The anorthite, however, has got very restricted application. The fired colour of a ferruginous clay also deepens appreciably if it be mixed with feldspars. In Part I of the present series (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 425) it has been pointed out that the adventitious minerals in clay, more particularly the feldspars, play an important rôle in the reduction of ferric iron. This reduction causes a definite change in the shade of the fired colour. The present communication deals with the experiments made with a view to explaining the mechanism of ferric iron reduction in fused feldspars. This would eventually furnish some informations that are wanting in the observations of the previous workers. For reasons mentioned above, the study was confined mainly to soda and potash feldspars.

It will be of interest to preface a short note concerning the structure of feldspars and their most striking properties. According to Machatschki (*Ctbl. Min.*, 1928, A, 97), the structure of feldspars is based on frameworks of linked SiO_4 and AlO_4 tetrahedra, with the cations K, Na, Ca or Ba situated in the interstices of the negatively charged framework of tetrahedra, and it has been confirmed by X-ray analyses by Taylor and his co-workers (*Z. Krist.*, 1933, 85, 423; 1934 87, 464). It is further revealed from X-ray analyses that in orthoclase, the potassium atoms lie on the reflection planes, fitting into cavities and that each potassium atom has ten oxygen atoms around it at approximately equal distances. In albite, however, the sodium atom is surrounded by a group of six or at the most seven oxygen atoms at different distances. This shows that the alkalis in feldspars do not form real "bridges" between the tetrahedra. Secondly, the valency of each cation is satisfied as a result of partial contribution from the neighbouring oxygen atoms (Pauling's Principle, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1010). If these deductions be correct, the logical conclusion is that the cations of feldspars can be rapidly detached from their combination under favourable conditions. In fact, the feldspars are all highly alterable minerals and their alteration products are both numerous and important. They are attacked by water alone, more so, by water containing carbon dioxide, and still more vigorously by acid waters, such as issue from volcanic vents or are formed by the oxidation of sulphides. Alkaline solutions also exert a powerful decomposing action upon this group of silicates. Among the numerous experiments, relative to this class of reactions, those of Daubrée ("Etudes synthétiques de géologie expérimentale", 1879, pp. 268-275) are perhaps the most classic. Fragments of orthoclase were agitated with water alone by revolution in a cylinder of iron during 192 hours. From 5 kg. of the feldspar, 12.6 g. of K_2O were found in the filtered solution. Water charged with CO_2 and 2 kg. of orthoclase, after 10 days of agitation, yielded 0.27 g. of K_2O and 0.75 g. of free silica. Again, according to Seger, if a mixture of clay and feldspar be exposed to porcelain heat, the alkalis are separated which then act on the clay producing no vitreous mass. If, however, quartz be added to the mixture, the separated alkalis react with it and yield a vitreous and glossy mass, which is characteristic of porcelain (Bose, "Modern Pottery Manufacture", 1947, p. 81). All

these facts lend strong support in favour of the conclusion regarding the cations in feldspars.

Moore (*J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1949, 33, No. 154, p 267) has explained the conditions which determine the state of oxidation of metallic oxides introduced as coloring agents into glass. He has adduced conclusive proof to establish that in a mass of molten soda or potash-lime glass, reduction is to be expected. This is because of the high temperatures employed in melting, and also because the ions of the alkali metals assist in the dissociation of oxides that attain instability. If the arguments concerning the stability of the alkali metals in feldspars be accepted as valid, the reduction mechanism of ferric iron, either inherent or incorporated, in a mass of molten feldspar can be explained in an analogous way.

Thus, high temperatures favour simultaneously the dissociation of ferric iron, separation of alkali metals as ions and increased fluidity of the molten feldspar. This latter assists in promoting a rapid rate of diffusion of the alkali ions and thereby facilitates contact between the ions and the oxides that have already attained instability. Under such conditions the ferric iron acts as oxygen-donor and the ions, after accepting these oxygens, are converted into R_2O . Depending on the progress of reduction, the reduced iron may have a composition like $Fe_3O_4^+$ or FeO^+ . After losing its ionic charge, the reduced oxide appears to enter the structure yielding a new product. There are, however, some evidences for considering that iron does, perhaps, enter into the structure. Thus, the watery extract of the glassy melt contains measurable quantity of the alkalies. Secondly, the added iron cannot be easily brought into solution even by heating with concentrated acids.

Arguments in favour of the reduction mechanism admit of the following additional deductions:

1. The percentage of ferric iron remaining constant, the extent of reduction should depend on the concentration of Na_2O or K_2O of the respective feldspars.
2. The reaction takes place in a mass of fused or semi-fused silicates and as such, the process of re-oxidation, under oxidising furnace condition, is confined only to the surface. The percentage of Fe_2O_3 will therefore depend on its rate of diffusion at the surface and on the total surface area exposed.
3. The iron in the solidified melt from any feldspar and a ferrous compound should remain in the fully ferrous condition provided that the atmosphere is either reducing or a neutral one.
4. The fired colour of the fused product must be different, depending on the ratio of ferrous to ferric iron.
5. Moore (*loc.cit.*) has pointed out that the mechanical obstruction to be experienced by a potassium ion during its migration through a glassy melt must be greater than that of a sodium ion.

This is because the former is heavier than the latter and, in addition, it has a larger ionic diameter. As the extent of reduction depends on the contact between the ions and the oxides, the yield of ferrous iron should be more in albite than in orthoclase melt. It may be pointed out that excepting the item (5), the experimental results are in complete

agreement with the deductions. The yield of ferrous iron in orthoclase is greater than that in albite. An attempt has been made to explain this anomalous feature and this will appear in the experimental portion.

The entire plan of study embraces investigation in greater detail into the extent of reduction of ferric compounds in orthoclase and in albite melts under different atmospheric conditions. Iron compounds, used in the present study, comprise ferric silicate, ferric and ferrous oxalates, ferric nitrate and magnetic oxide of iron. A measure of both ferric and ferrous forms of iron in the solidified fused mass was obtained by the adoption of the method outlined by Mellor ("A Treatise on Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1938, p. 513). The colour of each product was noted by a visual examination. Albite and orthoclase, used for different experiments, were collected from Rupnarainpur and Jagadishpur respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Both orthoclase and albite were separately ground to pass 250 mesh sieve. Different batches were made up from orthoclase or albite and iron compounds. The proportion of the latter was increased up to a maximum of 5%. Each batch was intimately mixed in a pot mill during 24 hours. A separate sillimanite pot, having a high resistance to corrosion by the fused mass, was used for each experiment. The heating was done mostly in a muffle furnace with a door provided with two openings, which helped in maintaining either a fully oxidising or a fully reducing atmosphere inside the furnace. Excepting a few cases, all other experiments were conducted at 1310°. The rate of firing was controlled and the maximum temperature was reached during 18 hours. The muffle was cooled to the room temperature during 12 hours. For a comparative study, the furnace conditions were reproduced as accurately as possible for all experiments. The temperature of the muffle was recorded by a platinum-rhodium thermocouple. After each experiment, the solidified melt was removed by breaking the container and its colour estimated visually. This was next analysed for the percentages of both ferric and ferrous iron. Table I gives the analyses of the feldspars used.

TABLE I

Substance.	SiO ₂ .	Al ₂ O ₃ .	Fe ₂ O ₃ .*	FeO.	CaO.	MgO.	Na ₂ O.	K ₂ O.	Loss.
Orthoclase *	64.01%	19.54%	0.71%	0.13%	0.43%	0.06%	2.52%	12.40%	0.30%
Albite	68.45	17.80	0.57	0.11	0.50	0.18	11.24	0.62	0.57

* Total iron as Fe₂O₃.

The total percentage of the alkalis is greater in orthoclase than in albite. This is also the case with iron, which is one of the inclusions in feldspars (Table I). It is rather difficult to explain how iron could exist mostly as the ferric iron in feldspars. However, this ferric iron too suffers reduction if the feldspars be fused or simply exposed to a temperature of incipient fusion. This will be apparent from Table II, which shows the extent of reduction of intrinsic ferric iron when feldspars are subjected separately

to a temperature of 1310°. Actual analysis shows that, in each case iron is practically reduced to the ferrous state, although the entire operation is conducted in air.

TABLE II

Feldspars alone. Atmosphere-air.

Substance.	Colour of the solidified glassy melt.	% Iron in the solidified melt as	
		FeO.	Fe ₂ O ₃ .
Albite	Pale bluish green	0.62	Slight trace
Orthoclase	Do	0.77	Do

It is generally agreed that oxides of iron are responsible for different tints of feldspars. A feldspar changes its hue due simply to calcination process. No satisfactory explanation has yet been offered for this change. From the results in Table II it appears that we have a partial explanation for such a change.

It can be claimed that the results of initial experiments partially corroborate the expectation. With a view to adducing further evidences, powdered feldspars were artificially impregnated with increasing proportions of ferric or ferrous compounds and the progress of reduction in each case was studied in the usual way. Experiments were conducted in atmospheres like air and carbon monoxide and each sample was slowly cooled in the muffle. Tables III to VII record such results.

TABLE III

Albite and orthoclase containing increasing amounts of ferric silicate.

Batch.	Atmosphere.	Colour of the solidified melt.	% Iron as	
			FeO.	Fe ₂ O ₃ .
Albite + 1% ferric silicate	Air	Pale green	0.68	0.41
	CO	Deep green	0.91	0.06
Do + 2% ..	Air	Deep green	1.21	0.402
	CO	Deep bluish green	1.69	0.030
Do + 4% ..	Air	Deep blackish green	2.48	0.31
	CO	Deep bluish green	3.01	0.004
Do + 5% ..	Air	Deep bluish green	3.07	0.38
	CO	Almost black	4.20	Trace
Orthoclase + 1% ..	Air	Brilliant pale yellowish green	0.97	0.32
	CO	Bluish green	1.28	0.003
Do + 2% ..	Air	Yellowish green	1.501	0.28
	CO	Deep bluish green	1.84	Trace
Do + 4% ..	Air	Deep greenish blue	2.71	0.201
	CO	Deep bluish green	4.18	Trace
Do + 5% ..	Air	Dark greenish blue	3.8	0.26
	CO	Almost black	4.32	Trace

TABLE IV

Albite and orthoclase containing increasing amounts of ferric nitrate.

Batch.	Atmosphere.	Colour of the solidified glassy melt.	% Iron as	
			FeO.	Fe ₂ O ₃ .
Albite + 1% ferric nitrate	Air	Faint yellowish green	0.302	0.52
	CO	Deep yellowish green	0.66	0.206
Do + 2% "	Air	Greenish	0.58	0.501
	CO	Bluish green	0.88	0.170
Do + 4% "	Air	Deep yellowish green	0.71	0.58
	CO	Deep bluish green	1.01	0.103
Do + 5% "	Air	Deep bluish green	0.98	0.44
	CO	Deep bluish black	1.43	0.06
Orthoclase+1% "	Air	Faint yellowish green	0.60	0.53
	CO	Bluish green	0.94	0.20
Do + 2% "	Air	Yellowish green	0.81	0.506
	CO	Bluish green	1.20	0.180
Do + 4% "	Air	Deep bluish green	1.140	0.510
	CO	Deep blackish blue	1.449	0.103
Do + 5% "	Air	Dark bluish green	1.22	0.46
	CO	Dark blackish green	1.58	Trace

TABLE V

Albite and orthoclase containing increasing amounts of magnetic oxide.

Batch.	Atmosphere.	Colour of the solidified glassy melt	% Iron as	
			FeO.	Fe ₂ O ₃ .
Albite + 1% magnetite	Air	Yellowish green	0.89	0.37
	CO	Bluish green	1.19	0.06
Do + 2% "	Air	Deep yellowish green	2.006	0.21
	CO	Deep bluish green	2.130	0.09
Do + 4% "	Air	Deep greenish blue	4.04	0.18
	CO	Deep blackish blue	4.20	0.04
Do + 5% "	Air	Dark bluish green	4.8	0.26
	CO	Dark blackish green	5.91	0.10
Orthoclase+1% "	Air	Yellowish green	0.97	0.401
	CO	Bluish green	1.27	0.08
Do + 2% "	Air	Deep yellowish green	2.1	0.31
	CO	Brilliant green	2.3	Trace
Do + 4% "	Air	Deep bluish green	4.26	0.11
	CO	Deep blackish blue	4.32	Trace
Do + 5% "	Air	Deep blue	4.96	0.38
	CO	Deep blackish blue	5.20	Trace

The results in Tables III and IV show many features of interest :

Ferric iron suffers increased reduction in orthoclase than in albite. Secondly, the influence of atmosphere, which is confined only to the surface, is also appreciable.

Thirdly, the products of decomposition of ferric nitrate tend to retard the reduction of ferric iron. These last two facts appear to be of special interest for those connected with glass technology. Ordinarily, for preventing the development of iron colour in glass, batches are so proportioned as to include some oxidising agent in them. The

TABLE VI

Albite and orthoclase containing increasing amounts of ferric oxalate.

Batch.	Atmosphere.	Colour of the solidified glassy melt.	FeO.	% Iron as Fe ₂ O ₃ .
Albite + 1% ferric oxalate	Air	Pale greenish blue	0.61	0.02
	CO	Deeper bluish green	0.64	Trace
Do + 2% "	Air	Deep greenish blue	0.83	0.02
	CO	Deep bluish black	0.86	Trace
Do + 4% "	Air	Dark bluish green	1.27	0.04
	CO	Dark blue	1.32	Trace
Do + 5% "	Air	Dark bluish green	1.50	0.08
	CO	Dark bluish black	1.56	Trace
Orthoclase + 1% "	Air	Pale greenish blue	0.61	0.08
	CO	Light bluish green	0.689	Trace
Do + 2% "	Air	Deep greenish blue	0.903	0.08
	CO	Deep bluish black	0.980	Trace
Do + 4% "	Air	Dark greenish blue	1.36	0.06
	CO	Dark bluish green	1.41	Trace
Do + 5% "	Air	Dark bluish green	1.61	0.106
	CO	Dark bluish black	1.70	Trace

TABLE VII

Albite and orthoclase containing increasing amounts of ferrous oxalate.

Batch.	Atmosphere.	Colour of the solidified glassy melt.	FeO.	% Iron as Fe ₂ O ₃ .
Albite + 1% ferrous oxalate	Air	Pale blackish green	1.008	Trace
	CO	Deeper blackish green	1.01	Trace
Do + 2% "	Air	Deep bluish green	1.66	Trace
	CO	Deep bluish black	1.668	Nil
Do + 4% "	Air	Dark green	2.90	Trace
	CO	Dark blackish green	2.90	Nil
Do + 5% "	Air	Dark green	3.307	Trace
	CO	Dark bluish black	3.32	Nil
Orthoclase + 1% "	Air	Pale bluish green	1.08	Trace
	CO	Light blackish green	1.085	Nil
Do + 2% "	Air	Deep bluish green	1.70	Trace
	CO	Deep blackish green	1.71	Nil
Do + 4% "	Air	Dark bluish green	2.93	Trace
	CO	Dark blackish blue	2.94	Nil
Do + 5% "	Air	Dark bluish green	3.43	Trace
	CO	Dark blackish blue	3.445	Nil

furnace conditions too are so adjusted as to give the appropriate type of atmosphere. It appears from Table IV that the oxidising agents cannot be totally effective in maintaining iron in the 'fully ferric' condition in all-soda or all-potash glass, unless their proportions be appreciable under oxidising furnace conditions. These observations, however, are not in accord with the conclusion made by Densem and Turner (*J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1938, 22, 372) in respect of iron colour in highly alkaline glasses.

Table VI shows that the tendency for reduction to occur is favoured also by the organic part of the iron compound. This therefore gives increased percentage of ferrous iron. Practically there is no change in the state of oxidation of iron in the batch containing "fully ferrous" iron (Table VII), and this is in accord with our anticipation.

In all the previous experiments different batches were subjected to heat treatments under identical conditions of temperature and duration so as to make a comparative study. In order to establish that the reduction of ferric iron in feldspars could take place gradually, batches were prepared from orthoclase or albite containing 1% and 2% of pure ferric oxide. Each batch was ground and intimately mixed in a pot mill till the entire quantity could be sieved through 200 mesh. A period of 18 hours was devoted for raising the temperature of each to 1310° and the duration of soaking was varied between 1 and 3 hours. The cooling was effected in course of 12 hours. Throughout the process, a current of dry air was maintained. A measure of both ferrous and ferric iron in the fired mass was made and Table VIII includes such results. It will be seen that the percentage of FeO increases with increased duration.

TABLE VIII

Effect of time on progress of reduction in feldspars.

	Added Fe ₂ O ₃ .	% Iron in raw mix.		% FeO in the fired mass after			% Fe ₂ O ₃ in the fired mass after		
		FeO.	Fe ₂ O ₃	1 hr.	2 hrs.	3 hrs.	1 hr.	2 hrs.	3 hrs.
Ortho- clase	1%	0.101	1.68	0.96	0.99	1.03	0.72	0.68	0.64
	2	0.072	2.65	1.35	1.50	1.66	1.22	1.04	0.88
Albite	1	0.09	1.53	0.76	0.81	0.86	0.78	0.72	0.67
	2	0.06	2.50	1.77	1.30	1.44	1.25	1.11	0.95

From the experimental results it is now obvious that potash and soda feldspars do influence the state of oxidation of iron, whether intrinsic or impregnated or both. In Part I of the present series (*loc. cit.*) it has been shown that the percentage of ferrous iron is much higher in a fired mixture of clay and iron if the latter suffers partial vitrification. Since both clay and feldspars constitute important ingredients of body or glaze mixtures for ceramic wares, it was considered useful to study the state of oxidation of iron in a fully vitrified porcelain body. The body was prepared from Simultollah China clay (25%), Rajmahal China clay (20%), potash feldspar (30%) and quartz (25%). The slip from this was freed from extraneous iron by a strong electromagnet. A few cups were prepared by slip casting. On an average, the bone-dry bodies contained 0.15% FeO and 0.51% Fe₂O₃. Some of these were fired in

a muffle furnace in an atmosphere comprising air, nitrogen, carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide in equal proportions by volume. The rest, however, were fired in a 12 feet diameter down-draught kiln along with other porcelain bodies. The temperature in each case was raised to 1310° , but the total durations were limited to 60 and 90 hours, respectively. The porosity of the vitrified mass was practically nil in each case. Table IX gives details relating to the fully vitrified bodies.

TABLE IX

Total Fe as Fe_2O_3 in the bone-dry body.	Vitrified in.	Duration.	Colour of the vitrified body.	% Iron in the vitrified body as		Total Fe as Fe_2O_3 in the vitrified body.
				Fe_2O_3 .	FeO.	
0.68%	Muffle	60 hrs.	Faint bluish green	0.167	0.38	0.593 %
	Kiln	90	Do	0.138	0.40	0.587

The ratio of ferrous/ferric iron appears from Table IX to be much higher in fully vitrified bodies. To test if this applies to bodies containing higher proportions of iron, further experiments were conducted with batches from the above porcelain composition and different proportions of ferric silicate (Fe_2O_3 , 71.01%). Excepting temperature, all other conditions were maintained the same. Three sets of experiments were conducted with each batch at temperatures like 1200° , 1250° and 1310° and the results have been tabulated below (Tables X - XII).

TABLE X

Porcelain body plus ferric silicate.

Temp. = 1200° .

Silicate.	Total Fe as Fe_2O_3 in bone-dry body.	Fired in.	Duration.	Colour of the fired body.	% Iron in the fired body as		Total iron as Fe_2O_3 in the vitrified body.
					FeO.	Fe_2O_3 .	
1%	1.36%	Muffle	60 hrs.	Cream	0.32	0.938	1.30%
		Kiln	90	Do	0.31	0.94	1.29
2	2.006	Muffle	60	Yellowish brown	0.46	1.46	1.98
		Kiln	90	Do	0.42	1.47	1.96
4	3.39	Muffle	60	Deep brown	0.58	2.5	3.34
		Kiln	90	Do	0.52*	2.69	3.32
5	4.003	Muffle	60	Chocolate	1.07	2.703	3.92
		Kiln	90	Deep brown	1.12	2.65	3.908

Results in Tables X to XII present some interesting features. The percentage of ferric iron predominates in those samples that have not suffered vitrification. Its proportion gradually diminishes with corresponding increase in the yield of ferrous iron as vitrification progresses. The yield of FeO is markedly high even if the stage of incipient vitrification is just reached. All these observations add additional support to our earlier view that vitrification inhibits the chance of re-oxidation with corresponding change in the tone of the fired colour.

TABLE XI

Porcelain body plus ferric silicate.

Temp. = 1250°.

Silicate.	Total iron as Fe ₂ O ₃ in bone-dry body.	Fired in.	Duration.	Colour of the fired body.	% Iron in the fired body as		Total iron as Fe ₂ O ₃ in vitrified body.
					FeO.	Fe ₂ O ₃	
1%	1.36%	Muffle	60 hrs.	Cream	0.56	0.664	1.29%
		Kiln	90	Do	0.53	0.69	1.28
2	2.006	Muffle	60	Yellowish brown, incipient vitrification	1.24	0.581	1.96
		Kiln	90	Do	1.30	0.511	1.94
4	3.39	Muffle	60	Deep brown, sinters.	2.516	0.482	3.29
		Kiln	90	Do	2.54	0.462	3.301
5	4.003	Muffle	60	Blackish brown, sinters hard.	3.101	0.492	3.94
		Kiln	90	Do	3.13	0.43	3.91

TABLE XII

Porcelain body plus ferric silicate.

Temp. = 1310°.

Silicate.	Total iron in bonedry body.	Fired in.	Duration.	Colour of the vitrified body.	% Iron in the vitrified body as.		Total iron as Fe ₂ O ₃ in the vitrified body.
					FeO.	Fe ₂ O ₃	
1%	1.36%	Muffle	60 hrs.	Greenish brown	1.03%	0.12%	1.28%
		Kiln	90	Yellowish brown	1.06	0.105	1.264
2	2.006	Muffle	60	Brown mass	1.49	0.271	1.91
		Kiln	90	Do	1.51	0.203	1.003
4	3.39	Muffle	60	Blackish brown	2.601	0.31	3.28
		Kiln	90	Deep chocolate	2.76	0.21	3.28
5	4.003	Muffle	60	Deep blackish brown, metallic lustre	3.20	0.306	3.901
		Kiln	90	Do	3.262	0.28	3.89

From the results concerning feldspars, it has been suggested in the introduction that the alkalis in them are loosely bound and that some of them perhaps are not re-accommodated in the tetrahedral structure when fused with ferric iron. If this be correct, the question centres round the state of existence of the displaced alkalis. Since this admits of diverse suggestions being made, one of such probabilities is that the alkali metals may form soluble compounds with silica and then remain uniformly distributed in the solidified melt. A satisfactory verification of such a deduction can be made from a study of (i) the total quantity of alkalis extractable from 100 g. of the powdered melt, (ii) the total quantity of iron that passes into solution on being treated with different acids (both dilute and strong) and (iii) the total quantity of silica or alumina separated from the fused mass when treated with water.

For a measure of the alkalis, displaced from the structure, powdered albite or orthoclase was intimately mixed with ferric oxide (4%) and the mixture was exposed to 1310° for 4 hours. The total duration of heating, soaking and cooling involved 30 hours. The solidified melt was powdered to pass through a 200 hole sieve. The powder was dried at 100° and after cooling in a desiccator, 5 g. were weighed out in a platinum basin. This was then heated for 1 hour on a water-bath with 100 c.c. of distilled water, the loss of water being made good by occasional fresh additions. The liquid was then filtered and the residue thoroughly washed with distilled water, the runnings having been added to the filtrate. The filtrate was next titrated with $N/50\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Another 5 g. sample was autoclaved with 100 c.c. of distilled water for 1 hour at 2 kilos pressure and the extract was similarly titrated. These experiments were also repeated with pure albite or orthoclase under identical conditions (Table XIII).

TABLE XIII

Alkalis separated from albite or orthoclase.

Material.	Alkalis separated from 100 g. of the melt.	
	Water-bath.	Autoclave.
Albite alone	Slight trace	Slight trace
Albite +4% Fe_2O_3	1.82 g.	2.03 g.
Orthoclase alone	Trace	Trace
Orthoclase +4% Fe_2O_3	1.84 g	2.06 g.

The results in Table XIII show that the alkalis in feldspars are displaced by iron and that they are extractable. This is, however, not true of pure albite or orthoclase. In this respect the results are not in agreement with those recorded by Daubrèe (*loc. cit.*). Naturally, these experiments were repeated with slight modifications. Thus, instead of 5 kilos of potash feldspar, we started with 1 lb. of previously powdered albite or orthoclase for each experiment. Each specimen was agitated separately with the same quantity of water for 72 hours, both in an all-porcelain pot mill and in an iron drum of almost identical shape and size. The slip from each could be easily made to pass through 250 mesh sieve. This was then filtered and washed in the usual way. Table XIV shows the results of such experiments.

TABLE XIV

Material.	Alkalis in the extract from	
	Pot mill.	Iron drum.
Albite.	Slight trace	0.104 g.
Orthoclase	Trace	0.183

It is thus clear that the presence of iron is not beneficial to the stability of the alkalis in feldspars and this is perhaps a striking observation.

The iron in the melts appears to be in a very stable state of combination, as this cannot be brought into solution by heating with acids (both dilute and strong). This

was tested by treating the powdered samples (5 g. each) separately with acids (100 c.c.) for 1 hour and filtering. The extract and the washings were analysed for iron in the usual way and Table XV shows the results of such analyses.

TABLE XV

Material.	Acid.	Iron as Fe_2O_3 in the extract from		Remarks.
		Diute acid.	Strong acid.	
Albite melt	HCl	0.007 g.	0.04 g.	Calculated for 100 g. of the powder.
	HNO_3	0.004	0.031	
	H_2SO_4	0.0051	0.038	
Orthoclase melt	HCl	0.0073	0.052	
	HNO_3	0.0046	0.036	
	H_2SO_4	0.0057	0.054	

It is rather difficult to get an exact measure of the silica or of alumina that may be separated due to the action of ferric iron on feldspars. An approximate idea was, however, made by adopting a rather crude procedure. A definite weight of the pulverised fused mass (200 mesh) was treated separately with caustic soda solutions of various strengths on a water-bath for 24 hours and the proportions of both alumina and silica were estimated in the extract. Stronger alkali solution was not used as it exerted a powerful decomposing action upon the feldspars. The specific gravity of the residue from each was also determined. Table XVI gives rather a crude picture of such experiments.

TABLE XVI

Orthoclase.

Alkali conc.	Al_2O_3 .	SiO_2 .	Sp. gr.
N/40	0.033 %	0.114 %	2.180
N/30	0.080	0.360	2.166
N/20	0.130	0.520	2.150
N/10	0.170	0.640	2.140
N/5	0.270	0.880	2.120
N	0.450	1.030	2.090

The results point out that, relatively, the proportion of SiO_2 is higher than that of alumina and, as such, the possibility of formation of the sodium silicate exists.

Before concluding, it would be of interest if a brief reference to the usefulness of the glassy melt from feldspars and iron oxide for glaze purpose be made. A few compositions were tried for producing a good brown glaze for stoneware jars and the following are some of the recipes that have given satisfactory results.

TABLE XVII

	1.	2.	3.		1.	2.	3.
Melt	38	44	38	Marble	16	15	—
MnO_2	6	7	6	Quartz	37	38	37
Fire clay	10	15	10	Potash feldspar	6	—	—
China clay	5	—	5	Soda	—	—	6
				Whiting	—	—	16

Further work on other feldspars is in progress.

DISCUSSION

It has been conclusively established that ferric iron does suffer reduction in feldspar melt and that the resultant colour of the fired mass depends on the relative proportions of the oxides of iron and on the nature of compounds they produce. Strikingly enough, the tendency for reduction to occur is definitely greater in orthoclase than in albite. From a study of oxidation-reduction effects in glass, Moore (*loc. cit.*) has found that the tendency of ferric iron towards reduction is less marked in 'all-potash' glasses than in 'all-soda' glasses of the corresponding composition. "The potassium ions are heavier than the sodium ions and will therefore migrate more slowly through the glass; but, in addition, the potassium ions are larger than the sodium ions and will therefore have a greater difficulty in passing through the mesh-like structure formed by the SiO_4 tetrahedra".

The argument of Moore is though convincing, the fact concerning enhanced reduction of ferric iron in orthoclase remains. It is therefore proposed to offer some plausible explanation for this anomaly. The total percentage of the alkalis in orthoclase is greater than that in albite and this must be one of the reasons for an increased yield of ferrous iron. The way in which the alkali metals are accommodated in the glass structure is perhaps not similar to that in feldspars. This will be evident from the fact that a mass of powdered potash or soda-lime-silicate glass, on being simply treated with water, gives a definite test for the alkalis. Feldspar powders do not, ordinarily, respond to such a test. Again, there is evidence that a glass containing potassium oxide is somewhat more stable towards water than the corresponding glass with an equal weight of sodium oxide as its alkalis. From our findings (Table XIV) it may be said that feldspars behave differently. The concentration of the alkalis in water, under modified conditions of experiment, is greater from potash feldspar than from the soda variety. These two facts point out that the stability of a sodium atom in glass structure is perhaps analogous to that of a potassium atom in orthoclase. This observation appears also to be in accord with known facts concerning feldspars. Thus, orthoclase alters rather easily to kaolinite or to sericite. The change occurs both under weathering and hydrothermal conditions. Relatively, however, albite is more stable under hydrothermal conditions.

All experiments were made with natural feldspars which are never pure. It has been shown that natural orthoclase usually contains about 20% of $\text{NaAlSi}_3\text{O}_8$, besides very small amounts of other molecules such as $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$, $\text{RbAlSi}_3\text{O}_8$, etc. Albite contains up to 10% $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$ and up to about 5% KAlSi_3O_8 , as well as minor amounts of other molecules (Winchell, "Elements of Optical Mineralogy", 1932, Part II, 3rd. Ed., pp. 364-68). The results of ultimate chemical analyses of our specimen appear in Table I. A calculation of the mineralogical composition of each sample was made from the results of chemical analysis by the adoption of the procedure outlined by Washington (*J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, 1918, 1, 405). On the basis of this, the sample of orthoclase is found to contain 21.3% of $\text{NaAlSi}_3\text{O}_8$ and 2.2% $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$. The albite specimen contains 3.6% KAlSi_3O_8 and about 2.4% $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$. It will be seen that the potash feldspar is more sodic and the reverse is not well marked in albite.

It is therefore to be expected that the fluidity of the molten mass from potash feldspar must be higher than that from albite at 1310° . Increased fluidity assists in greater freedom of movement of the ions. Again, in order to account for the sub-parallel lamellar structure in perthites, it has been accepted that in molten condition both sodium and potassium atoms are evenly distributed through the network (Shand, "Eruptive Rocks," 1947, p. 15). If both the alkalis in greater amounts are available simultaneously for reduction, the progress would relatively be great. All these, coupled with the reasonings already made above, should perhaps be the reason for enhanced reduction in orthoclase.

The colored product, prepared pyrogenically from orthoclase and ferric oxide, can advantageously be used as an ingredient for stoneware glazes. Its importance lies in the fact that, relatively, it can impart increased brilliancy to the glaze. A study of the chemical nature of the product is thus a necessary prerequisite to a better understanding of the reason why such improvement occurs. In fact, investigations are in progress with a view to obtaining further data for elucidating the course of reaction. From data already recorded in the present paper and from some of those in progress, there is some justification in considering the product to be a mixture of $\text{FeAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$, KFeSi_3O_8 and unchanged orthoclase. From analogy with known feldspars, these compounds may be designated as iron analogue of anorthite or iron plagioclase and iron orthoclase respectively. It is proposed to discuss, if the formulae, assigned to the two different compounds, are theoretically possible. If so, what may possibly be the courses of reaction.

Chemical analyses of the thoroughly washed powdered mass show that there has been definite change in the composition. Now, variation in composition may be caused by inclusion, regular intergrowths or by solid solution. Again, there are three principal types of solid solution: substitutional (or proxy), interstitial and defect. It needs deciding which of these probabilities, if any, is there. Since the percentage of the alkalis are appreciably lower than what is expected theoretically, the change cannot be due to inclusion. Phenomenon like intergrowths is only possible if there be a solid solution of two or more crystals first. The question of orientation of the precipitated phase within the host crystal is a subsidiary one. Pending any decision regarding the structure and chemical nature of the compound, the idea of ex-solution intergrowths appears to be superfluous. It cannot be due to defect lattice, as there is no available literature to show that vacancy actually exists in the structure of feldspars due to missing atoms. Even, if it were a fact, the total percentage of the alkali metals ought not to have gone down. This is also precisely the reason why the change should not be regarded as due to regular interstitial solid solution where atoms are being added and none removed. It is therefore to be seen if the variation in composition is due to replacement of alkali atoms by iron atoms and also due to similar change between iron and aluminium. The former accounts for the formation of iron analogue of anorthite and the latter for iron orthoclase.

It has long been customary to think of the feldspar family in terms of the three end-members: orthoclase, albite and anorthite. The structures of these are more amenable to substitution and, as such, they give rise, by isomorphous crystallisation,

to several series of solid solutions. The substitution of Ca-Al for Na-Si in the network is a matter of common occurrence. This accounts for the presence of varieties of feldspars in nature. Besides, there are a lot of feldspars containing cations other than Na, K, Ca or Ba, and so the idea of an iron feldspar is not unusual. Again, most of the natural feldspars have been synthetically produced either pyrogenically or under hydrothermal conditions from their constituents or by the breaking down of other more complex silicates ("Synthèse des minéraux et des roches", p. 138; "Manuel de minéralogie", 1862, vol. I, pp. 277, 543; *Compt. rend.*, 1877, 85, 952). Feldspars, analogous to anorthite, oligoclase, and labradorite, but containing strontium, barium or lead in place of calcium, have also been obtained synthetically by Fouqué and Lévy (*Synthèse des minéraux et des roches*", p. 145). Plagioclase feldspars containing potassium have been made by Dittler (*Min. pet. Mitt.*, 1910, 29, 273). Recently, Goldsmith (*J. Geol.*, 1950, 58, 518) has prepared compounds of gallium and germanium that are isostructural with the feldspars. He has shown that in the Na and K feldspars, Al^{3+} and Si^{4+} can be completely replaced by Ga^{3+} and Ge^{4+} ; but in pure Ca feldspar, complete substitution cannot be made. From a consideration of these facts, the idea of the formation of compounds like $FeAl_2Si_3O_8$ and $KFeSi_3O_8$ does not seem improbable. The change may be represented as taking place in the following way :

In the first equation, for each Fe^{2+} ion introduced in place of K^+ , an extra positive charge is simultaneously introduced. This is, however, compensated by a similar substitution of Al^{3+} for Si^{4+} in the structure and the double substitution $Fe^{2+} + Al^{3+} = K^+ + Si^{4+}$ causes no net change in valence charges. Similarly, the mechanism of the second equation can be explained. Separations of alkalis, silica and alumina from the feldspars and retention of iron, mostly in the ferrous form, appear to lend support in favour of the proposed scheme of reactions.

According to Goldschmidt's empirical rules (Norton, "Refractories", 1942, 2nd Ed., p. 59) none of the proposed scheme of reaction is a case of isomorphous substitution. For, the possibility of isomorphous substitution depends more upon ionic size than upon valency, and ions readily interchange if they are equal both in charge and size. The substitution is also possible even if radii of the similar atoms differ from each other by less than approximately 15% of the radius of the smaller atom. There is more than 15% difference between the radii of Fe^{2+} (0.83 Å) and K^+ (1.33 Å) or between Fe^{2+} (0.67 Å) and Al^{3+} (0.57 Å).

Again, on the basis of Pauling's principle (*loc. cit.*) these iron compounds cannot be iso-structural with the natural feldspars. For, in order to be classed as a feldspar, it is essential to have a structure having linked tetrahedral groups containing silicon and aluminium. If, now, a similar structure be assumed for the proposed iron analogue of anorthite, it will not be possible to justify the same by the application of Pauling's principles. Thus, the oxygen linked to aluminium and silicon has a valency of one-

fourth left unsatisfied. A ferrous iron forms octahedra! co-ordination and, as such, its contribution is only one-third. Naturally it cannot balance a deficiency of one-fourth. From similar considerations it is not possible to assign a feldspar structure to the proposed iron orthoclase. It may, however, be pointed out that in the latter case, the oxygen linked to iron and silicon has a valency of one-half and this can readily be balanced by the large monovalent potassium ions, since they are surrounded by eight oxygens.

It now transpires that the formulae, provisionally assigned to the iron compounds, are quite possible according to the ordinary laws of valency and from chemical analyses. On the other hand, they cannot be classed as feldspars if the rules formulated by Pauling and Goldschmidt be considered. Literatures show that Pauling's rules are applicable mostly to silicates found in nature and that these laws are not well obeyed in cases of artificially prepared silicates (Bragg, "Atomic Structure of Minerals", 1937, p. 37). Likewise, Goldschmidt's empirical rules are not beyond exceptions. Many instances are known where isomorphous substitutions do take place even though the radii of atoms differ by more than 15% (Norton, "Refractories", 1942, p. 60). The existence of iron orthoclase molecule in feldspar has also been suggested by Faust (*Amer. Min.*, 1936, 21, 735). If these exceptions be given any credence, it may be concluded that, pending X-ray and other analyses, the idea of grouping the iron compounds as feldspars cannot be ruled out altogether.

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